

Using Machine Learning Methods in the Diagnosis of Meningioma

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ABSTRACT

Meningioma is one of the most common tumors that recur after resection (GTR), and the World Health Organization (WHO) classification of brain tumors and the prediction of the risk of recurrence of the disease continue to attract the attention of researchers. Therefore, we analyzed 117 cases of meningioma, a benign brain tumor originating from meningotheelial cells of the arachnoid membrane of the brain, registered in 2024 at the National Center for Pathology, based on histopathological diagnosis and epidemiology, and used artificial intelligence (AI)-based software (R, Python), machine learning (ML) methods, methods, and algorithms to make age, gender, grade, calculations, and comparisons. Using machine learning methods, we can predict which age and gender are the most common and which grade of meningioma is most common. Although it is widely studied in many countries, the lack of studies conducted using machine learning in our country is the reason for starting this study.

KEYWORDS: Meningioma; ICD-10; Machine Learning (ML); K-means; Cluster Analysis HCPC (PCA, MFA); meningioma grading

ARTICLE DETAILS

Published On:
25 May 2026

Available on:
<https://ijmscrs.com>

I. BACKGROUND

Meningioma is the most common primary brain tumor in adults, accounting for approximately 20% of all brain tumors. The annual incidence of new cases is 1.3–7.8 cases per 100,000 population, with a higher incidence in women (some studies have reported a female:male ratio of 2:1). The incidence tends to increase with age. It is very rare in children, accounting for a small proportion of all childhood brain tumors. Between 2015 and 2019, 515 new cases of CNS tumors were reported in the Mongolian National Cancer Registry, with an incidence of 3.7 cases per 100,000 population, with 4.2 in men and 3.4 in women. 57.6% of these CNS tumors were gliomas, and the exact incidence of meningiomas is not reported. A study by the International Agency for Research on Cancer noted that the prevalence of meningiomas depends on factors such as exposure to ionizing radiation, trauma, hormonal influences, heredity, and adult mobile phone use. According to the World Health Organization (WHO) 2016/2021 classification.

WHO Grade I (Benign)

- 80–95% of all cases
WHO Grade II (Atypical)
 - 4–19/10 HPF mitoses, high cell density, or brain invasion
 - 15–20% of all cases
WHO grade III (Anaplastic/malignant)
 - 20/10 HPF with mitoses or papillary or rhabdoid morphology
 - Rare, accounting for 1–5% of all cases.

In the pathological diagnosis of meningioma, the WHO classification of grade and type is of great importance in predicting the prognosis and treatment of the disease, so we used machine learning methods to study the relationship between patient age, gender and grade in the diagnosis of brain tissue.

II. RESEARCH METHODS AND TECHNIQUES

Method 1: A total of n = 117 (adult) cases of meningioma were included. (n = 89) cases were included in the program.

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Figure 1. Age and gender classification

In the case of Meningioma, the most susceptible age and gender categories are 54-56 years for men and 58 years for women, and 56-58 years for the overall age group.

Method 2: Cluster analysis HCPC(PCA)

Clustering: Data Cluster Analysis based on R program were divided into clusters using PCA algorithms of HCPC (Hierarchical Clustering on Principal Components) method. (Han and Kamber., 2006 n.d.), (HCPC - Hierarchical Clustering on Principal Components 2017), (Josse and Husson 2012).

Analysis: The distance between clusters is measured by the formulas of minimum distance, (Figure 2)

Minimum distance:

$$dist(c_i, c_j) = \min_{p \in C_i, p' \in C_j} \{|p - p'|\} \min \quad (1)$$

Maximum distance:

$$dist(c_i, c_j) = \max_{p \in C_i, p' \in C_j} \{|p - p'|\} \max \quad (2)$$

Mean distance:

$$dist_{mean}(c_i, c_j) = |m_i - m_j| \quad (3)$$

Average distance:

$$dist_{min}(C_i, C_j) = \frac{1}{n_i n_j} \sum_{p \in C_i, p' \in C_j} |p - p'| \quad (4)$$

Four widely used measures for distance between clusters are as follows, where $|p - p'|$ is the distance between two objects or points, p and p' ; m_i is the mean for cluster, C_i ; and n_i is the number of objects in C_i .

Figure 2. Cluster analysis of the total data divided into 3 clusters

The total Meningioma grade cases were divided into 3 clusters based on the similarity of the principal components in the cluster analysis.

Method 3: k - Means

A centroid-based partitioning technique uses the centroid of a cluster, C_i , as the representative of that cluster. Conceptually, the centroid of a cluster is its center point. The centroid can be defined in various ways such as by the mean or medoid of the objects (or points) assigned to the cluster. The difference between an object $p \in C_i$ and c_i , the representative of the cluster, is measured by $dist(p, c_i)$, where $dist(x, y)$ is the Euclidean distance between two points x and y . The quality of cluster C_i can be measured by the within-cluster variation, which is the sum of squared error between all objects in C_i and the centroid c_i , defined as.

$$E = \sum_{i=1}^k \sum_{p \in C_i} dist(p, c_i)^2, \quad (5)$$

Where E is the sum of the squared error for all objects in the data set; p is the point in space representing a given object; and c_i is the centroid of cluster C_i (both p and c_i are multidimensional).

k - Means classification method was used to classify meningioma, WHO grade I and II cases by age and similar values in grade I and II types.

Figure 3. K-means classification

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Here are the types of similar diseases, including total meningioma, WHO grade I and II cases (Table 1):

Table 1. Meningioma, WHO grade I, II.

D32 - II	D32 - I	D32.0 - II	D32.0 - I	D32.1 - I	D32.9 - I
2	52	1	17	3	14

The k – Means classification method is a benchmark for all meningiomas, WHO grade I and II cases, and similar disease types.

Figure 4. Similarity model for k – Means classification

Here, the total incidence is shown graphically, with age and grade I and II being the most common.

Method 4: The total number of meningiomas, WHO grade I and II, is summarized as follows:

Figure 5. Meningioma, WHO grade I and II cases, summary

Here, the overall age dependence is 58 years, with D32 – Type I being more dependent, respectively.

III. RESULTS OF EXPERIMENTS AND RESEARCH

Calculations

The calculations were performed for a total age of $n=89$ cases (Table 2)

Table 2. Age-specific characteristics of meningiomas, WHO grades I and II

Age	
Min.	:17.00
st Qu.	:50.50
Median	:59.00
Mean	:57.16
3rd Qu.	:65.50
Max.	:78.00

Here, the most susceptible age for meningioma is 78 years old, the least susceptible is 17 years old, the average age is 57 years old, and the most susceptible age is between 58 and 59 years old. Here it corresponds to the specifications of (Figure 1).

Classification

The main dimensions that are most common in a cluster are measured in the following areas.

Result: $n=89$

	v.test	mean	overall	sd	in	overall	p.valu
		in	mean	sd	in	sd	e
		catego			category		
		ry					
\$'1'	6.059	1.5	0.0714	0.5	0.3375	1.3662	
d32.	407		2857		583	e-09	
1							
\$'2'	-	1.047	1.4523	0.7221	1.2574	3.9285	
d32	.06118	619	81	786	04	e-02	
age	-	44.09	54.976	10.234	14.186	9.0567	
	4.911	5238	190	8832	661	e-07	
	099						
\$'3'	3.642	2.583	1.4523	1.4409	1.2574	0.0002	
d32	431	333	81	68	04	700	
age	3.004	65.50	54.976	7.9214	14.186	0.0026	
	102	0000	190	90	661	636	
\$'4'	4.732	1.428	0.4047	0.4948	0.6195	2.2188	
d32.	396	571	619	717	0	54e-06	
9							
age	2.196	65.85	54.976	7.1199	14.186	2.8069	
	310	7143	1905	633	6606	76e-02	
d32.	2.072	1.142	0.5476	1.1248	0.8223	3.8204	
0	654	857	190	583	770	53e-02	

This indicates that the average incidence of type D32 disease in (clusters 2 and 3) is 44 – 65 years old, with an overall average incidence of 54.97 percent.

IV. CONCLUSION

The results of the study were analyzed using machine learning (ML) methods and algorithms to perform cluster analysis, classification, calculation, and comparison on the ICD-10 D32 types of brain tumors registered at the National Center for Pathology laboratories in 2024.

1. Men are most susceptible to the disease between the ages of 54 and 56, women are the ages of 58, and the

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total age group is most susceptible to the disease between the ages of 56 and 58

2. In the cluster analysis of the total disease categories (clusters 2 and 3), the average incidence of D32 disease is 44 to 65 years old, and the overall average incidence is 54.97 percent
3. When classifying meningiomas by grade, grade 1 is predominant, grade 2 is rare, and grade 3 meningiomas are not found

Therefore, it is seen that grade 1 meningiomas are more common in people aged 56 to 58 years. Women are also more susceptible to the disease. A detailed look at the disease, age, and gender classifications, calculations, and comparisons shows the importance of using new technologies, AI, and ML machine learning methods in clinical diagnosis and consultation.

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